

THE PHENOMENON OF BILINGUALISM IN THE WORKS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK DIASPORA WRITERS

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Annotation: *This study is devoted to the analysis of the phenomenon of bilingualism in the works of English and Uzbek diaspora writers. The work highlights the linguopoetic and cultural-aesthetic features of bilingualism formed in the diaspora environment. The study comparatively examines the artistic manifestations of code exchange, language hybridization, and the expression of cultural identity in the works of English and Uzbek writers. Also, the phenomenon of bilingualism reveals the mechanisms of interaction between language and culture in the creation of a literary text and is interpreted as an important factor in the development of modern transnational literature.*

Keywords: *bilingualism, diaspora literature, English writers, Uzbek writers, transnational literature, linguopoetics, code exchange, cultural identity, bilingualism, language hybridity.*

In recent decades, as a result of the intensification of globalization and migration processes, linguistic and cultural multifaceted phenomena, in particular, the phenomenon of bilingualism, have begun to occupy a large place in scientific attention. Bilingualism is a person's ability to know two languages simultaneously and use them effectively in different contexts. This phenomenon manifests itself as an interesting object of study not only in linguistics, but also in the fields of literary studies and cultural studies. Through literary texts created in two languages, they not only express personal identity, but also serve as a bridge between two cultures. English-language diaspora literature, for example, in works created by Uzbek writers, is presented to a global readership while preserving the cultural and linguistic elements of the Uzbek language. At the same time, through writing in English, they will have the opportunity to reinterpret their cultural heritage in a new context. The phenomenon of bilingualism manifests itself in the works of Uzbek and English diaspora writers not only as a language issue, but also as a means of forming cultural identity, expressed through cultural identification, memories, and symbolic images. In this context, this study aims

to analyze the literary and cultural aspects of bilingualism, as well as the interactions and transformations between two languages in the works of diaspora writers. The main tasks of this work are:

1. Identification and classification of the phenomenon of bilingualism in the works of English and Uzbek diaspora writers;
2. Analysis of strategies for expressing cultural identity through bilingualism;
3. Studying the transformation of language and culture in bilingual texts through literary means.

The theoretical and practical significance of the article lies in the fact that, through the analysis of bilingual literature, it reveals the mechanisms of cultural identification in the works of diaspora writers and scientifically illuminates the role of bilingualism in the creative process. Bilingualism is the ability of a person to communicate effectively in two languages, which includes a complex interaction between language and culture (Grosjean, 1982; Baker, 2011). The phenomenon of bilingualism is divided into linguistic, cognitive, and cultural components: A) **Linguistic component**: lexical and grammatical knowledge in two languages; B) **Cognitive component**: the ability to think logically and abstractly in the process of learning and using language; C) **Cultural component**: the ability to express cultural identity and cultural messages in two languages.

Table 1. Components of bilingualism

Component	Definition	Expression in creative literature
Linguistic	Language knowledge, lexical and grammatical ability	Bilingual expressions in texts, code-alternation
Cognitive	Logical and abstract thinking in language use	Describe characters' comments in two languages
Cultural	Cultural identity and integration	Cultural references, symbolic images, traditional elements

2. Diaspora literature and bilingualism

In the works of diaspora writers, bilingualism manifests itself not only as knowledge of language, but also as a cultural bridge (Clifford, 1994; Ismailov, 2008). Diaspora texts often have the following features: Integration of cultural codes - the combination of elements of two cultures in the work;

Code-alternation - the alternating use of two languages in the text; Cultural transformation - the reinterpretation of Uzbek cultural elements in English.

Table 2. Bilingual means in diaspora literature

Means	Definition	Example
Cultural code	Characteristics of a particular culture	Uzbek holidays, customs, traditions
Code-alternation	Alternative use of language in text	Uzbek phrases with English dialogues
Cultural transformation	Representing cultural elements in a new language and context	Adapting Uzbek proverbs to English
Linguistic game	Tongue-twisters	English-Uzbek word games, metaphors

Bilingualism in the works of diaspora writers includes not only language proficiency, but also cultural expression. Through this, they achieve several important goals. First of all, with the help of bilingualism, writers have the opportunity to preserve their cultural identity and express it through creative texts. This, in turn, serves to preserve the Uzbek cultural heritage, customs, and traditional values in a new language and context.

Also, bilingualism provides the reader with a new linguistic and cultural experience. Through code-alternation in texts, cultural references, and bilingual expressions, the reader becomes acquainted not only with the language, but also with another culture, which enriches the literary experience and helps to understand it in a global context.

In addition, bilingualism serves as an effective communicative bridge between two cultures. The texts of diaspora writers connect English and Uzbek cultures, allowing the reader to understand and appreciate both cultures. Thus, bilingualism manifests itself not only as a means of expressing language and culture, but also as an effective mechanism for ensuring creative and cultural integration.

Table 3. Creative functions of bilingualism

Function	Definition	Sample
Cultural identity	Preserving one's cultural identity	Customs of Uzbek heroes in the work
Aesthetic value	Stylistic and artistic coloring of the text	Creating rhythm and melody through code alternation

Communication bridge	Means of communication between two cultures	English-speaking student understands culture	Uzbek culture
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Theoretical analysis shows that bilingualism manifests itself in the works of diaspora writers as a central phenomenon expressing the interdependence of language and culture. Based on the table and examples, the following main conclusions can be drawn:

1. The components of bilingualism (linguistic, cognitive, and cultural) allow writers to use two languages not only as a means of communication, but also as a means of cultural identity and creative expression.
2. In diaspora literature, the tools of bilingualism - code-alternation, cultural codes, and cultural transformation - help writers to harmonize Uzbek and English cultures, while also providing the reader with a new cultural and linguistic experience.
3. Through creative functions, bilingualism performs the function of cultural identification, the creation of aesthetic value, and a communicative bridge between two cultures.

In general, bilingualism is important in the work of diaspora writers not only as a language ability, but also as a means of expressing cultural identity and actively participating in global cultural communication. Thus, the phenomenon of bilingualism becomes a central element in the literary process, combining integration, aesthetic, and communicative functions.

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